

Jan (samba season). Samba rice is always less productive because of cold weather coupled with pests and diseases. A medium to fine rice grain type is preferred by farmers.

Breeding line P.837, a derivative of the cross IR8/H.4, appears promising for this area. It matures in 145-150 d. Grains are medium slender and translucent. Yields average 5.8 t/ha, an increase of 29, 22, and 23% over IR20, Co 43, and Mahsuri puthae (white ponni), respectively.

P.837 has recorded resistance to such major pests as brown planthopper and leaffolder. It was tolerant of the major diseases blast and helminthosporium (see table). □

Field reaction^a of P.837 to major insects and diseases, compared to check varieties. Pondicherry, India, 1984-87.

Variety	Insects			Diseases		
	BPH	Leaffolder	Stem borer (%)	Blast	Helminthosporium	Sheath rot
				<i>1984-85</i>		
P.837	3	3	8.5	1	3	3
IR20	9	3	14.0	1	7	5
				<i>1985-86</i>		
P.837	3	3	9.0	3	3	1
IR20	7	5	18.5	5	7	3
Co 43	5	7	16.0	5	5	7
				<i>1986-87</i>		
P.837	—	—	10.2	—	3	5
IR20	—	5	16.0	—	7	7
Co 43	—	7	16.5	—	3	7
Co 1009	—	5	14.5	—	5	5

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Gall midge (GM)-resistant rice cultivars

N. Kulkarni, P. P. Reddy, and S. S. Rao, Agricultural Research Station, Warangal 506007, Andhra Pradesh, India

So far three varieties resistant to GM—Kakatiya, Surekha, and Pothana—have been released for general cultivation. Cultivars suited to different cropping practices and with improved grain type also are needed.

One local practice is sowing rice under dry conditions and converting to irrigation when water is available in tanks. Two short-duration, GM-resistant varieties—WGL 18011(CR44/W.12708) and WGL 20471-97 (BC.5/W.12708)—were sown in the 1987 wet season (WS) using the local seed drill at 30-cm spacing in 73.2 m² plot. This dry condition was converted to wet conditions at 40 d.

Both varieties matured in 100 d and yielded 3.0 t/ha. They have long slender grains. In minikit tests in the dry season (DS), WGL 20471-97 averaged 6.3 t yield/ha, 47% higher than Tella Hamsa. Both varieties are suitable for late, direct sowing.

Two GM-resistant cultures—WGL 44645 and WGL 48684—have superior grain quality. WGL 44645 (WGL 23022/Surekha) has a 125 d duration in

WS and 135 d in DS. It has stiff straw and long slender grains. Grain quality is superior to that of varieties released earlier. In minikit trials, it yielded 4.2 t/ha against 2.8 t/ha for Tella Hamsa. It is tolerant of stem borer and hispa.

WGL 48684 (WGL 27120/(Mashuri/WGL 17672)/Surekha) has a 135 d duration in WS. Grains are medium slender. It is also suitable for DS provided sowing is before December.

Both varieties have 9% protein content. □

TR-RNR-21, a new medium-duration rice variety, released in Andhra Pradesh (A.P.)

P. Narahari, Nuclear Agriculture Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC), Trombay, Bombay 400085, India

TR-RNR-21 is a derivative of the cross IR8/TR-5. TR-5 is a N_f-induced dwarf mutant of salinity-resistant SR-26-B.

In initial yield evaluations in 1972-78, it gave 54% higher yields than Jaya in the wet season and 19% in the dry

season and compared favorably with IR8 and Sona.

Compared with Pankaj, Jaya, RP-4-14, Sona, Surekha, RNR-32341, and Prabhat, in 1975-80 trials, TR-RNR-21 gave average yields 10.1% higher than those of the highest yielding checks and 19.8% higher than the average of 7 checks (see table). In minikit trials at more than 90 sites in 9 districts of Telangana region, mean grain yield (3.8 t/ha) was 19% higher than yield of local checks. TR-RNR-21 was released in 1987 as Hari, for general cultivation

Relative yield performance of TR-RNR-21 (Hari) at Andhra Pradesh Agriculture University and in the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India.

Variety	Mean yield (t/ha)		
	Monsoon season (5 trials)	Dry season (6 trials)	Total
TR-RNR-21 (<i>Hari</i>)	5.4	6.3	5.9
Highest yielding check	4.9	5.8	5.4
All checks combined	4.7	5.1	4.9